

ABSTRACT BOOK

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toxin-related diseases have increased dramatically in the past 60 years. Hence, there is need to explore some source which can combat the effect of synthetic pesticides. Fungi as a group are well known for their production of chemically diverse compounds, some of which are biologically very potent. Different fungal biopesticides can be used to control plant diseases as well as insect pests and weeds. The entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria bassiana* is well characterized and have been approved by the United States Environmental Protection Agency as a pest biological control method. However, thousands of other fungi are unexploited and it is important to identify and use different fungi for biocontrol. The aim of this study was to identify new fungal entomopathogens that may be used as potential biocontrol agents. In this study, 16 different fungi having biological origin has been isolated. Out of which one showing maximum insecticidal activity was selected. The insecticidal potential of this fungus was further evaluated by forming different concentration against *S.litura* a polyphagus pest of commercial crops. The toxicity bioassay revealed that fungus induced mortality in *S.litura*, inhibited the emergence of adults from pupa and also caused various deformities. These observations indicated the potential of fungus as the simple, inexpensive and accessible source of bioinsecticide to manage polyphagus pests like *S.litura*.

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HOST PLANT RESISTANCE (HPR) STUDY IN JAMUN (*SYZYGIUM CUMINI*) AGAINST FRUIT BORERS, *MERIDARCHIS SCYRODES* MEYRICK AND *DUDUA APROBOLA* (MEYRICK) IN SEMI-ARID REGION

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Plants genotypes possess different antixenotic and/or allelochemical properties, which resultantly induce in them different mechanisms of resistance. Various phenotypic traits including, pulp: stone ratio, pulp thickness, fruit width and fruit length and allelochemical traits including tannins, phenols, total alkaloid and flavonoid contents of fruit were studied on twenty six genotypes of jamun, *S. cumini* in relation to resistance

against fruit borers, *Meridarchis scyroides* Meyrick and *Dudua aprobola* (Meyrick) under field conditions in the semi-arid region of India. The significant differences were found in percent fruit borer, *Meridarchis scyroides* Meyrick and *Dudua aprobola* (Meyrick) among the tested genotypes during 2014-15. GJ-26, GJ-27 (Katha Jamun), GJ-19, GJ-17 and GJ-15 were found to resistant; GJ-3, GJ-6, GJ-7, GJ-9, GJ-13, GJ-16, GJ-18, GJ-20, GJ-23, GJ-24 and GJ-25 moderately resistant; GJ-4, GJ-8, GJ-10, GJ-12, GJ-14, GJ-21 and GJ-22 were susceptible and GJ-1 and GJ-GJ-11 highly susceptible genotypes. The percent fruit infestation of fruit borer, *M. scyroides* was highest in genotype GJ-1 (64.70%) followed by GJ-11 (62.07%). The minimum percent fruit infestation of fruit borer, *M. scyroides* was observed in GJ-27 (Katha Jamun) (8.23%) followed by GJ-17 (10.03%). The per cent infestation of *D. aprobola* was highest in GJ-1 (76.30 %) and lowest in GJ-27 (Katha Jamun) (10.80 %) followed by GJ-26 (11.13 %). The percent fruit infestation of fruit borer, *M. scyroides* and *D. aprobola* were significantly lower in resistant germplasm and higher in susceptible genotypes. Tannins, phenols, total alkaloid and flavonoid contents were significantly higher in resistant genotypes and lower in susceptible genotypes. Tannins, phenols, total alkaloids and flavonoid contents had significant negative correlations with percent fruit infestation of fruit borer, *M. scyroides* and *D. aprobola*. The fruit length (0.58 & 0.56), fruit width (0.33 & 0.32), pulp thickness (0.51 & 0.51) and pulp: stone ratio (0.61 & 0.63) showed significant positive correlations with percent fruit infestation of fruit borer, *M. scyroides* and *D. aprobola*. Based upon the above morphological and biochemical characters individually, it was impossible to group the entities as variables were not in agreement to each other. Hence, principal component analysis was performed to achieve parsimony and reduce the dimensionality by extracting the smallest number of components that accounted for most of the variation in the original multivariate data. Taking into consideration eight parameters viz., flavonoid content, total alkaloid, tannins content, phenols content, fruit length, fruit width, pulp thickness and pulp: stone ratio principal component analysis (PCA) was performed. Two principal components (PCs) were extracted with eigen value ≥ 1.0 , after varimax rotation with Kaiser normalization procedure which converged in three iterations. The extraction communalities for all the variables tested were ≥ 0.5 indicating that the variables were well represented by the extracted PCs which together explained a cumulative variation of 82.61 %. PC1 explained 59.92 % of the variation

while PC2 explained 23.42 % of variation. PC1 had the loadings for flavonoid content (0.91), tannins content (0.92), total alkaloid (0.89), phenols content (0.93), fruit length (-0.55) and pulp: stone ratio (-0.58). Fruit width (0.93) and pulp thickness (0.86) were loaded in PC2.

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IMPACT OF ELEVATED CARBON DIOXIDE ON FOOD PERFORMANCE INDICES OF *HELICOVERPA ARMIGERA* (HÜBNER)

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Climate change is possibly the most significant global change that has attracted the attention of scientific community all over the globe as it could alter population and ecosystem equilibrium (Kambrekar *et al.* 2015). Any change in climate would exert significant effects on the distribution and abundance of insect species, their natural enemies and hosts (Karuppaiah and Sujayanad 2012). It has also been estimated that the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere might rise to 550 ppm by as early as 2035 (Stern 2007). Keeping this in view, present studies focused on the effect of rise in CO₂ concentration on food consumption indices of *H. armigera* on tomato. The present study was conducted in digitally controlled Walk-in-type plant growth chamber in the Department of Entomology, PAU, Ludhiana, Punjab as per the methodology of Pandey *et al.* (2015) with slight modifications. Two concentrations of CO₂ (ambient: 400 ppm and elevated: 500 ppm) were selected at the alternating temperature regimes (max: min) of 25:12^oC with four replications. Using the data relating to larval weight, leaf weight consumed and faecal matter excreted, various food consumption indices were calculated using formula given by Waldbauer (1968). Treatment means were compared and separated using least significant difference (LSD) at p<0.05. The mean daily consumption by the larvae increased by 54.8 and 62.03 per cent at carbon dioxide concentration of 400 and 500 ppm, respectively in fifth instar. Similarly, mean consumption index by the larvae increased by 9.99 per cent with rise in carbon dioxide concentration from 400 to 500 ppm. While, the mean approximate digestibility value of the larvae increased by 7.64 per cent with rise in carbon dioxide concentration from